

Studies on Coagulation and Electrical Properties of Thorium Ferrocyanide, Thorium Succinate, and Cobalt Ferrocyanide Hydrosols

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The corrected ζ -potentials of thorium ferrocyanide, thorium succinate, and cobalt ferrocyanide sols have been determined, taking surface-conductance effect into consideration, and the coagulation phenomena have been explained in the light of the equation:

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma C_i$$

where ζ_a represents the ζ -potential of the sol at a total equicoagulating concentration of ΣC_i of counter ions in normality and A and B are constants. The limiting concentrations of the counter ions, beyond which surface-conductance effect vanishes, have also been calculated for the above sols.

Thorium ferrocyanide, thorium succinate, and cobalt ferrocyanide sols were prepared to study the effect of electrolytes on the ζ -potential and also their coagulation. The results are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sols.—Thorium ferrocyanide, thorium succinate, and cobalt ferrocyanide sols were prepared by peptising thoroughly washed precipitates of the compounds with thorium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide, respectively, followed by dialysis. The precipitates were obtained by mixing $M/20$ solutions of thorium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide, $M/10$ and $M/20$ solutions of sodium succinate and thorium nitrate, and $M/20$ solutions of cobalt nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide, respectively. After aging the sols were found to possess specific conductance of 9.60×10^{-3} , 7.31×10^{-3} , and 2.38×10^{-4} ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ at 25°, respectively. Cobalt ferrocyanide sol was negatively charged and the other two were positively charged.

Determination of Equicoagulating Concentrations and Measurement of ζ -Potential.—Determination of equicoagulating concentrations of different electrolytes and measurement of ζ -potential at different equicoagulating concentrations by electro-osmosis and micro-cathaphoresis in case of each of the sols were exactly similar to that described by Kundu and Moulik¹. The time allowed for coagulation was 15 min. and 2 min. for centrifuging at 2000 r.p.m. in each case. The ζ -potentials were calculated with the help of the Helmholtz-

1. This Journal, 1965, 42, 705.

Smoluchowski equation. The conditions were so adjusted that relaxation and electroviscosity effects became negligible²⁻³. The results are represented in Fig. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1.

Thorium ferrocyanide sol.

I—electro-osmosis.

II—microcataphoresis.

1: KNO_3 . 2: $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$.3: $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$.4: K_2SO_4 . 5: K-citrate.

Thorium succinate sol.

III—electro-osmosis.

IV—microcataphoresis.

1: KCl. 2, 3: $\text{KCl} + \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$.4: $\text{KCl} + \text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.5: K_2SO_4 . 6: $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.

Cobalt ferrocyanide sol.

V—electro-osmosis.

VI—microcataphoresis.

1, 2, 3: $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.4: $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 + (\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}(\text{NH}_2)_2(\text{HCl})_2$.5: $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.

DISCUSSION

As the surface-conductance effect is only prominent in the present experiments, one may apply Ghosh's equations⁴⁻⁵:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{S} \quad \dots \quad \text{for electro-osmosis} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m'}{S} \quad \dots \quad \text{for electrophoresis} \quad (2)$$

to obtain the ζ -potential corrected for surface-conductance effect (ζ) with the help of the measured ζ -potential (ζ_a) and bulk specific conductance (S). Fig. 2 represents the $1/\zeta_a$ vs. $1/S$ plots from which ζ -values for different sols and for different methods of measurement in case of each of the sols are found to be very close.

A straight line is expected when ζ_a values are plotted against $\log \Sigma C_i$, where ΣC_i represents the total equicoagulating concentration of the counter ions, in normality, used according to the equation:

2. Overbeek, "Colloid Science", Vol. I, edited by H. B. Kravt, Elsevier, 1960, p. 211.

3. Hunter and Alexander, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1963, 18, 620.

4. Ghosh, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 5, 121; *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 402.

5. Ghosh et al., *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 29.

$$\zeta_a = A + B \log \Sigma C_i \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

proposed by Kundu and Moulik¹. This expectation is fully corroborated as is evident from Fig. 1.

FIG 2
[Description of graphs and points are as in Fig. 1].

A combination of equations (1) and / or (2) with (3) should provide a concentration value beyond which surface conductance will play no part in the measurement of ζ -potential. This is obtained from $\zeta_a - \log \Sigma C_i$ curve.

A is a constant for a particular sol and B is a constant for a particular method of measurement of ζ -potential of a sol. The values of these constants are obtained from the graphs. These constants should play an important role in coagulation, as may be found by rearranging equation (3) to

$$\Sigma C_i = e^{(\zeta_a - A)/B} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

The coagulation, again, depends on the measured ζ -potential. Therefore the equi-coagulating concentration is found to depend, apart from valency of the counter ion used, on the lowering of the ζ -potential by the counter ion. The sols have been found to deviate from the Verwey and Overbeek's inverse sixth power valency rule and these deviations may be explained in the light of equation (4) above.

Table I represents the ζ -values corrected for surface-conductance effect, beyond the limiting concentration of which surface conductance does not play any part in the measurement of ζ -potential and the values of the constants A and B .

TABLE I

Sol.	ζ -Potential(mv)			Limiting conc.(<i>N</i>).			<i>A</i> (mv). $2.303B(\text{mv})/\log(N)$.		
	E.	M.	Mean	E.	M.	Mean.	<i>E</i> or <i>M</i> .	E.	M.
Th-ferrocyanide	21.2	22.2	21.7	3.80×10^{-3}	6.31×10^{-3}	5.06×10^{-3}	27.5	4.48	4.10
Th-succinate	25.0	26.0	25.5	3.16×10^{-3}	3.39×10^{-3}	3.26×10^{-3}	40.2	10.10	9.60
Co-ferrocyanide	28.3	27.5	27.9	2.88×10^{-3}	1.78×10^{-3}	2.33×10^{-3}	39.5	7.30	6.85

N.B.—E and M denote respectively "electro-osmosis" and "microcataphoresis".

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